

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: National Biodiversity Network Trust

Spatiotemporal analysis of priority
species records across England

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1 Executive summary

1.1 Background and data overview

The National Biodiversity Network (NBN) is a collaborative partnership created to exchange biodiversity information. The NBN Trust, the charity which oversees and facilitates the development of the Network, has a membership including many UK wildlife conservation organisations, government, country agencies, environmental agencies, local environmental records centres and many voluntary groups.

The NBN Trust promotes the sharing and use of biodiversity data, which is achieved through their digital data sharing infrastructure, the NBN Atlas. The Atlas (<https://nbnatlas.org/>) is the UK's largest publicly accessible source of biodiversity data. Biodiversity data (also known as 'biological records' or 'species occurrence data') is information about what species are found where.

We worked with a dataset extracted from the NBN Atlas comprising all records of the 943 species of principal importance in England from 1970 to 2020. These priority species were identified as being the most threatened and requiring conservation action under the UK Biodiversity Action Plan, and are used in nature conservation to support policy, decision making and nature recovery. However, the dataset included 911 species only, as not all the 943 species of principal importance have been recorded on the NBN Atlas in the time period. This dataset included 10,202,929 records.

1.2 Main objectives

The overall objective of this Data Study Group (DSG) were to develop tools to understand the comprehensiveness of the NBN Atlas as a biodiversity inventory, and to highlight the value and impact of sharing biodiversity data using a subset of the records available online. The DSG focused on developing creative ideas for tables, plots, maps and visualisations to represent the extent of the species of principal importance in England on the NBN Atlas.

The research questions were:

1. How can we best represent the coverage of the NBN Atlas?
2. How can we best represent gaps in the NBN Atlas?
3. How can we highlight the value that data providers bring to the Atlas?
4. How can we identify species that we do not have comprehensive coverage for?

1.3 Approach

We used five different approaches to address the four objectives:

1. The first approach consisted of building a species distribution model by combining the dataset provided by the NBN Trust with environmental data from external sources. This allowed us to
 - represent the coverage of the NBN Atlas,
 - represent potential recording gaps for species,
 - highlight the value that each data provider brings in terms of coverage of species.
2. The second approach involved defining attributes of the data providers, which were used to highlight the value that each data provider brings to the Atlas as well as to identify gaps in data from data providers. Moreover, clustering of the data providers on the basis of their attributes highlighted areas of strength and weaknesses among the data providers.
3. The third approach comprised descriptive data visualisations to highlight the impact of individual data providers by developing a prototype for a data provider dashboard displaying the contributions of a single data provider.
4. The fourth approach focused on identifying species that do not have coverage. It consisted of a method for prioritising species based on discrepancies in occurrence record density in a target area. This approach attempts to highlight species for enhanced data collection by identifying species with occurrence data at a lower density that

we might anticipate if we assumed that they occurred at a similar frequency to a representative region chosen for comparison.

5. Finally, the fifth approach comprised descriptive data visualisations to represent the coverage of the NBN Atlas and to represent some of its gaps by assessing the distribution of the sampling strategy across each county by defining a spatial sampling variance measure.

1.4 Main conclusions

The main achievements of the DSG are the development of new approaches, a new metric and prototypes of interactive online dashboards.

1. Combining the NBN Trust data with environmental data from external sources, we developed a model to predict the distribution of species. Moreover, this model can show data providers the influence of their data upon insights into species. This species distribution model was included in a prototype of an online dashboard.
2. In order to highlight the value that each data provider brings to the dataset and to identify gaps, we developed a prototype for a data provider dashboard displaying the contributions of a single data provider as well as their defining characteristics as identified by the clustering method.
3. To identify species that do not have coverage from the geographic distribution of the data, we developed a method for prioritising species based on discrepancies in occurrence record density in a target area compared to a comparison region. This method was also included in a prototype of an online dashboard.
4. We also assessed the distribution of the sampling strategy across each county and developed a prototype web application.

1.5 Limitations, recommendations and future work

All the methods that we suggested are intended to provide a starting point, as they all require further development and refinement, as well as full deployment to the full dataset.

The main limitation of this work is that a lack of records in a particular area could mean that a species is physically absent, or that it has not been recorded. As we cannot distinguish between these two possibilities, this is a weakness for all approaches that we suggested in this report.

All the proposed models require further work, as the limited time of the DSG did not allow a full exploration of their specifications. However, we provided an overview of the value that these models can bring to the understanding of the NBN Trust data.

We did not have enough time to consider the temporal dimension of the records in the NBN Atlas to assess the taxonomic coverage throughout time. This could be an avenue for future research.

Within the limited time of the DSG, we have focused our efforts mainly on geographical representation of the data. Another potentially insightful way to visualise the data, which we did not explore, could be by taxonomic groups, e.g. using dendrograms to separate the species into phylogenetic groups. Visualising the data in this way could help researchers and funding bodies to gain a better overview which taxonomic groups could benefit from increased efforts in sampling and sharing of observation records.

2 Introduction

The National Biodiversity Network (NBN) Trust is a small charity with a big plan – to make data work for nature. For more than twenty years they have been making biodiversity data accessible, to support better decisions about the natural world and to connect people with nature. The National Biodiversity Network is a collaborative partnership created to exchange biodiversity information.

The NBN Trust promotes the sharing and use of biodiversity data, which is achieved through their digital data sharing infrastructure, the NBN Atlas. The NBN Atlas (<https://nbnatlas.org/>) is the UK's largest publicly accessible source of biodiversity data. Biodiversity data (also known as 'biological records' or 'species occurrence data') is information about what species are found where. With more than 200 million records of 50,290 UK species, the NBN Atlas is widely used by nature

conservation bodies, wildlife trusts, national recording schemes, NGOs, and academics to support decision-making and scientific research. Those same organisations, and many more, contribute on average 300,000 records of UK wildlife sightings monthly to the NBN Atlas. It is a treasure-trove of wildlife information - an outstanding source of evidence for decisions about the natural environment and a vital resource to connect people with nature.

The NBN Trust champions the collection and use of biodiversity records and is keen to develop innovative visualisations to better showcase the data available on the NBN Atlas. As a small charity, it is vital that they demonstrate the value and importance of making biodiversity records publicly available. It is critical for data providers - and their funders - to ensure continued support for their work and for users to ensure that they have oversight of what records are on the NBN Atlas so that they can have confidence that their decisions are based on the most complete and highest-quality evidence.

This Data Study Group (DSG) worked with a dataset extracted from the NBN Atlas comprising all records of the 943 species of principal importance in England from 1970 to 2020. These priority species were identified as being the most threatened and requiring conservation action under the UK Biodiversity Action Plan, and are used in nature conservation to support policy, decision making and nature recovery. However, the dataset included 911 species only, as not all the 943 species of principal importance were recorded on the NBN Atlas within the time period. This dataset included 10,202,929 records.

The overall objective of this Data Study Group were to develop tools to understand the comprehensiveness of the NBN Atlas as a biodiversity inventory, and to highlight the value and impact of sharing biodiversity data, using a subset of the records available online. The DSG focused on developing creative ideas for tables, plots, maps and visualisations to represent the extent of the species of principal importance in England on the NBN Atlas.

The research questions were:

1. How can we best represent the coverage of the NBN Atlas?
2. How can we best represent gaps in the NBN Atlas?

3. How can we highlight the value that data providers bring to the Atlas?
4. How can we identify species that we do not have comprehensive coverage for?

As well as descriptive data visualisations, we implemented statistical and machine learning methods, and visualised their model outputs. Five different approaches were developed.

This report is organised as follows. Section 3 provides an overview of the dataset, and Section 4 includes an exploratory data analysis. In Section 5 we describe the five main approaches that were developed by the participants of the DSG, and the preliminary results that were obtained. The report will conclude with some final conclusions in Section 6 as well as some recommendations for future work.

3 Data overview

3.1 Dataset description

This dataset included 10,202,929 records from 1970 to 2020.

For each record, the dataset includes species name, taxon group, date of recording, public location (provided as a grid reference and also as latitude, longitude and radius), county, data provider and type of data provider, whether the record is verified, whether the record is from a Local or National Nature Reserve, National Park, or Site of Special Scientific Interest (SSSI).

For each record, we know which source dataset the record comes from, as well as related metadata: the name of the source dataset, the name of the data provider, the type of organisation of the data provider, dataset type (classification of the type of records in the dataset: sighting is an ad-hoc occurrence, survey is a record from a survey, mixed is a dataset of both ad-hoc and survey-based records), date the source dataset was created, how to cite the source dataset, a short description of the source dataset, whether any information has not been shared (for example exact location of the records) and license type.

3.2 Data quality issues

Several variables, such as the recording method, present a substantial number of missing values, but overall the data is clean and ready to use.

However, the availability of a substantial number of records at low resolution (more than 1km² or more than 10km²) does not allow their use in some models and visualisations. Moreover, the data contains duplicated entries.

In our analysis, we used the UK Biodiversity Action Plan (BAP) Level 1 classification provided with the data. This classification system groups species by characteristics such as by habitat (i.e. Terrestrial invertebrates, Marine species), which do not necessarily reflect relatedness. For example, while vascular and non-vascular plants are in separate categories, alga and turtles are grouped in the same category of Marine species. There could be great value in representing the data based on phylogeny instead, allowing scientists to interrogate the data for true taxonomic groups at the different levels of Kingdom, Phylum, Class, Order, Family or Genus.

4 Exploratory Data Analysis

The list of habitats and species of principal importance in England includes 943 species identified as priority habitats and species in the UK (UK BAP). The DSG worked with a dataset extracted from the NBN Atlas comprising all records of the 943 species from 1970 to 2020. However, the dataset included 911 species only, as not all species were recorded on the NBN Atlas within the time period of interest.

These species are split into the following groups (UKBN or UKBAP classification): birds, terrestrial mammals, herptiles, fungi (including lichen), non-vascular plants, vascular plants, terrestrial invertebrates, marine only species and fish. Figure 1 shows the distribution of priority species present in the dataset by UKBAP classification group, while Figure 2 shows the number of missing UK priority species in this dataset.

Figure 1: Number of UK priority species in the dataset grouped by UKBAP classification group.

The records are provided at different levels of resolution (Figure 3), with different confirmation status, different recording method (Figure 4), and different licence type.

Each record belongs to a dataset, and the dataset types are survey (89 datasets), ad-hoc sightings (18), or mixed (49) when the dataset contains records that are both from surveys and ah-hoc sightings. 252 datasets are missing this information.

Figure 2: Number of missing UK priority species in the dataset grouped by UKBAP classification group.

Figure 3: Number of records for each level of resolution.

Figure 4: Number of records of UK priority species in the dataset grouped by UKBAP classification group and colour-coded by the associated recording method.

4.0.1 County comparisons

The dataset from the NBN Trust spans across 66 vice-counties. Vice-counties represent geographical divisions of the British Isles, widely recognised and utilised for biological recording and other scientific data collection. This section presents a comparative study of these datasets at the county level, aiming to highlight geographical variances in total occurrence counts and occurrence density per km^2 for each UKBAP group.

Variations in Total Occurrence and Species Occurrence The 66 vice-counties under study demonstrate an average occurrence of 150,089, a median of 136,587, a maximum of 393,083, and a minimum of 3. South-west Yorkshire stands as the county with the highest occurrence, succeeded by West Norfolk, East Suffolk, South Lancashire, and South Hampshire (see Figure 5). The dataset contains only data collected from England, thus vice counties that cross the Welsh and Scottish borders including Montgomeryshire, Denbighshire, Dumfriesshire, Roxburghshire, Flintshire, Radnorshire, Berwickshire, and Breconshire are sparsely represented (Figure 6).

Furthermore, we calculated the total occurrence per km^2 to represent the spatial sampling density for each vice-county. This helps mitigate any bias that could arise due to differing area coverage across counties. Generally, a strong correlation is observed between total occurrence and spatial sampling density, wherein areas of high sampling or reporting are primarily located in the southern and north-central regions of England. The ranking of spatial sampling density, however, differs from that of total occurrence. South Hampshire, East Suffolk, Huntingdonshire, West Norfolk, and East Norfolk emerge as the top 5 sampled areas (see Figures 9 and 10).

Figure 8 illustrates the spatial sampling density for each UKBAP classification group across different vice-counties. The sampling for birds is widespread across England, with higher sampling particularly observed in the central and eastern regions. Terrestrial invertebrates, mammals, herptiles, and vascular plants exhibit a similar pattern to that of birds. Fish and marine species are understandably sampled more in coastal areas as compared to inland regions. Fungi and non-vascular plants, although

not extensively sampled, show higher sampling densities in the south and in certain vice-counties.

Regarding the nine groups of level 1 UKBAP, the dominant group is the birds with a total occurrence of 7,084,786 records, which corresponds to 66% of the dataset. Marine species and non-vascular plants are only reported with 7,744 and 8,636 total occurrences in the dataset, respectively, which might be the result of the limited number of data providers in this group. The spatial sampling density for each UK BAP classification group is provided in Table 1.

Rank	Group	Occurrences/ km^2
1	Bird	48.0
2	Terrestrial invertebrates	12.8
3	Terrestrial mammals	4.0
4	Herptiles	2.4
6	Vascular plants	0.48
7	Fungi	0.10
8	Non-vascular plants	0.06
9	Marine species	0.06

Table 1: Spatial sampling density for each UK BAP classification group

Figure 7: The map of spatial sampling density for each vice-county.

Figure 8: The map of UKBAP classification group for each vice-county.

4.0.2 Data providers

The dataset includes data from 120 unique data providers. The providers are classified into categories, and the distribution of these is shown in Table 2.

Type	Number of records
Local Environmental Records Centre	32
Environmental/conservation NGO	27
National Scheme or Society	21
Recorder or recording group	13
Wildlife Trust	10
National or central government	8
Commercial company/environmental consultancy	5
Academia and education	3
Museum, zoo or botanic garden	3
Biological Records Centre	1

Table 2: Types of Data Providers

4.0.3 Species

Figure 9 shows the number of unique species recorded for each 5 year period in the dataset.

The spatial pattern and intensity of sampling varies considerably by taxonomic group and across time. Mapping the species richness (that is, the total number of unique species) per 10km square per taxonomic group reveals some clear patterns, such as the highly recorded nature of birds (Figure 10) relative to the much patchier sampling effort for plants (Figure 11). Any patchiness also reflects whether local/regional groups share their records on the NBN Atlas and not just patchy recording. The number of records increases over time, and this is particularly apparent within terrestrial mammals. For example, there was a much larger number of 10km squares without data in 2011 compared to 2019 (Figure 12). Some groups show clear delineation of the areas containing their native habitats, such as marine species although there were some unexpected records of marine species in inland areas (Figure 13).

Figure 9: Number of unique species recorded for each 5 year period

5 Methods and results

5.1 Environment-based gap identification for target species

5.1.1 Method

In order to address the objectives, we combine the dataset provided by the NBN Trust with the environmental data from external sources (Figure 14). We aim to provide a framework and build a simple species distribution model using variables described in Table 3. Species distribution modelling uses algorithms to predict the distribution of species across geographic space and time using environmental data.

Climate data was sourced from the HadUK-Grid climate observations from the Met Office [2]. This included total annual precipitation, average daily average temperature, average daily minimum temperature, and average daily maximum temperature. Land Cover data was sourced from the UKCEH Land Cover Map 2018 [5], as the percentage of each aggregate land cover per 1km square [4]. The land cover types were further aggregated into 5 land classes: woodland (broadleaf and coniferous); agricultural (arable and improved grassland); semi-natural habitats (semi-natural grassland and mountain, heath and bog); water

Figure 10: Number of bird species recorded within each 10km square across England from 2011 to 2019

Figure 11: Number of vascular plant species recorded within each 10km square across England from 2011 to 2019

Figure 12: Number of terrestrial mammal species recorded within each 10km square across England from 2011 to 2019

Figure 13: Number of marine species recorded within each 10km square across England from 2011 to 2019

Figure 14: Model framework. Each grid cell predicts the probability of a specific species sighting using local climate and land cover data.

Variable	Type
Land-cover	Compositional
Mean temperature	Continuous
Max temperature	Continuous
Min temperature	Continuous
Average precipitation	Continuous
Survey Effort	Count

Table 3: Variable description

(coastal, freshwater and saltwater); and built-up areas. Due to the mismatch between the environmental and survey data mapping, coastal land area is unaccounted for (Figure 15).

We trained our model using the observations of the species occurrence in 2018 (Figure 16). Three species were picked to represent a range of data availability: high (*Passer domesticus*; house sparrow), medium (*Erinaceus europeus*; hedgehog), and low (*Muscardinus avellanarius*; hazel dormouse). The total number of records used per species can be found in Table 4.

Species	2018		2019	
	Used records	Total records	Used records	Total records
Dormouse	2182	2184	2125	2129
Hedgehog	19837	19880	26098	26129
Sparrow	98810	101412	102696	105285

Table 4: Used and available number of records. Used records discounts mismatched map data around the coastline.

Three types of statistical models were fit to each of the three species. For the purpose of showcasing the potential of such models, we selected three popular options for which the software is readily available and fast to implement, which was necessary given the short timescale of the DSG. The first is a generalised linear model (GLM), a flexible generalisation of ordinary linear regression, with only linear functions of each variable. The

Figure 15: Area of mismatch between datasets.

Figure 16: Maps showing the 2018 probability of presence (purple), standard error (red) and actual records (green) for *Passer domesticus*, *Erinaceus europeus* and *Muscardinus avellanarius* respectively.

second is a GLM with quadratic functions of each variable. The third is a model with splines on each variable within a Generalised Additive Model (GAM), which is a generalised linear model in which the linear response variable depends linearly on unknown smooth functions of predictor variables. To balance the dataset, a random sub-sample of the squares with no observations of the species (but observation of at least one other species) was used for each model fit for both the hedgehog and the hazel dormouse models, equal to the size of the number of total observations of the species in that year. This was not done for the house sparrow as over half of the grid cells contained an observation point. All models were generalised models with a binomial family, fit using the `mgcv` package in R [6]. A constant survey effort of 45 records across all species per 1km² (including priority species) was assumed for all model predictions.

We assessed model performance using the deviance information criteria, the area under the curve (AUC), and the root mean squared error, a popular metric to measure the accuracy of a predictive model, when predicting the 2019 data. An ROC curve (receiver operating characteristic curve) is a graph showing the performance of a classification model at all classification thresholds, while AUC (Area under the ROC Curve) provides an aggregate measure of performance across all possible classification thresholds.

While we did not include full results of the model evaluation in this report, our preliminary exploration suggested that the GAM had the best predictive performance for the 2019 data, and our data.

The GAM that was fit is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(\text{data}) = & \alpha + s(\text{woodland}) + s(\text{water}) + s(\text{agricultural}) + \\
 & s(\text{seminatural}) + s(\text{urban}) + s(\text{rainfall}) + \\
 & s(\text{averagetemp}) + s(\text{mintemp}) + s(\text{maxtemp}) + \\
 & s(\text{numberofobservations}),
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where α is a scalar and s is a single spline function fit using the default 10 knots.

For comparisons, we also implemented a spatially explicit model with a 2-dimensional spline over the region, that was fit for each year from 2015 to 2020 inclusive.

5.1.2 Results

Overall, the 2018 predictions show a good degree of predictive power around areas of high clustering, especially for the hedgehog data (Figure 16). Using the trained model, we predicted the probability of presence for the following year, 2019 (Figure 17). Areas of high predicted presence of all 3 species are reflected in the observed data. These results provide some evidence that this model has the potential to adequately predict the presence of each species given the environmental conditions, land cover data and survey effort.

Figure 17: Maps showing the 2019 probability of presence (purple) and actual records (green) for *Passer domesticus*, *Erinaceus europaeus* and *Muscardinus avellanarius*.

Model performance varied across the different species, with the model of sparrow occurrence performing generally worse than that of the dormouse and hedgehog (Table 5). This is potentially due to sparrows being uniformly present across the country, therefore rendering the model unable to delineate predictors of sparrow occurrence. The deviance explained by the models of dormouse occurrence was generally higher than that of the hedgehog models, but the ability to predict data in 2019 was similar. The sparrow model performed poorly in predicting the 2019 data, as shown by the lowest AUC among the models considered (AUC takes values between 0 and 1, with higher values indicating better predictive power). Overall the GAM presented in Equation (1) had the best performance out of the three models considered, and we focus on the results of that model below.

Both 2018 and 2019 data show hazel dormouse data to be sparse and

Species	Model	Deviance explained	AUC
Dormouse	GLM	36.1%	0.807
Dormouse	GLM (quad)	48.4%	0.841
Dormouse	GAM	51.8%	0.851
Hedgehog	GLM	24.7%	0.874
Hedgehog	GLM (quad)	27.1%	0.876
Hedgehog	GAM	28.6%	0.879
Sparrow	GLM	13.9%	0.552
Sparrow	GLM (quad)	15.8%	0.588
Sparrow	GAM	16.6%	0.588

Table 5: Model performance for each model type and species

concentrated in the south of England. One potential use of such a model for users interested in the hazel dormouse distribution would be to identify areas of interest; whether it be by county or by OS grid reference (Figure 18). A large section of south-west England is predicted with high certainty (≥ 0.8) to have hazel dormouse however none have been recorded in 2019 within the highlighted grid cells. This may indicate an effort gap in data recording or a lack of data sharing from data providers.

Influence of individual data providers on species distribution predictions In order to show data providers the influence of their data upon insights into species, we demonstrate changes in model predictions of species distributions with and without their data. While these results fit naturally into the prototype presented in the next section on understanding data providers, we keep these results in this section as they are built on the GAM model developed above.

As an example, we selected hedgehog occurrences within the five vice-counties of Derbyshire, Nottinghamshire, Leicestershire, North Lincolnshire and South Lincolnshire within the year 2018 (Figure 19). This area is of particular interest as it contains four main data providers, each in a unique part of the region, and in varying intensities. In total, there were 2154 hedgehog observations, of which 70% was provided by the People’s Trust for Endangered Species (PTES), 20% by the British

Figure 18: Areas of high probability (≥ 0.8) and no recorded data of *Muscardinus avellanarius* occurrence.

Trust for Ornithology (BTO), 7% by the Mammal Society (MS) and 3% by NatureSpot (NS). Some of the data providers cover the entire region, such as the PTES, while others such as NatureSpot only provide data for a smaller area within the region (Figure 19).

From the full dataset, data provided by the four main data providers were removed sequentially and a GAM was run for each scenario with the aforementioned environmental co-variates. This allows a comparison between hedgehog occurrence predictions and model uncertainty.

The spatio-temporal model included no environmental co-variates, and the overall explanatory power of the model was poor (deviance explained around 15%) but it can be used to demonstrate how the contribution of each data provider informs our knowledge of the species of interest without the constraint of sourcing and matching to environmental data.

Figure 19: Records of hedgehogs across Lincolnshire, Derbyshire, Nottinghamshire, and Leicestershire by six data providers in 2018.

With the environmental model, as expected, the removal of the PTES dataset has the largest influence on the model results as they account for 70% of all observations (Figure 20). However, the standard error of the model is much lower, indicating that while the model is predicting a much lower hedgehog occurrence, it is more confident about that. This shows how model-based uncertainty and smaller datasets can lead to false certainty. A way to address this bias is to validate the model using observations from outside the training data, such as the previous and/or next years. The spatio-temporal model also showed a greater influence of removing PTES from the data, however it can also be seen that this removal has different effects in different years (Figure 21). In 2020, the proportion of the data that is provided by PTES is higher as there is no data from BTO, so removing the PTES data results in a much lower

predicted mean hedgehog occurrence.

Figure 20: Predicted mean number of hedgehog occurrences within each 1km square (top) and standard error of the prediction (bottom) for the complete model and the model missing each of one of the four main data providers.

Weaknesses and limitations The ability of a species distribution model to be useful in predicting where a species may be found is dependent on having both informative environmental predictors and enough data to make a useful model. In this report, we focused on three case study species which had at least a moderate number of records per year, as this approach is unlikely to work for species with only a handful of records. This approach is also by necessity limited by the presence of records, and while we tried to account for survey effort, there is still much scope for the model to miss areas that are good habitats for the species just because there are few records in that habitat within the NBN Atlas.

Figure 21: Change in mean model prediction when removing the data provider - spatio-temporal model. Given as the difference between the model without the data provider and the model with all data providers.

The nonconformity in data being provided presented another challenge for the model development. The Met Office and UKCEH Land Cover Map consisted of different mapping methods hence a large amount of data around the coastline was lost. Although this doesn't affect the species explored within this report, this could prove to be quite important for coastal species. It is also to be noted that the NBN dataset contains records with no or coarse (greater than 1km²) spatial information which were discarded. The downsides of the model highlights the importance of uniformity in the data provided and data-sharing from all data providers. Moving forward, a system is required in place to create a dataset with uniform spatial information across all data providers, preferably one that matches with the environmental datasets. As each species interacts uniquely with their environment, this method should be coupled with expert knowledge of the species and the regions of interest.

Future Work Potential avenues for modelling rare species include calculating simple indices of environmental similarity and identifying similar areas to previous records based on that. Alternatively, information from species that are more common and known to coexist with the rare species could be included in the model to help predict the distributions of those rare species. More careful consideration of which environmental and survey effort information is used to predict species, particularly more common species such as the sparrow, could lead to more useful model results. Further evaluation of modelling methods, and the most useful way to present results for different purposes, is required before making this approach operational.

Our models within this work do not explicitly take into account spatial or temporal resolutions of the data, and future work could involve including these effects within the modelling. There is also the potential to consider seasonal effects or other potential drivers of population dynamics.

5.2 Understanding data providers

5.2.1 Methods

To highlight the value that each data provider brings to the dataset and to identify gaps in data from data providers, we analyse the attributes of the 120 data providers and then cluster them into groups accordingly.

We have identified the following attributes of data providers.

- **Number of taxon groups:** Number of taxon groups provided by each data provider
- **Number of records:** Number of records provided by each data provider
- **Spot place precision:** Grid size resolutions of the records that they provided
- **Spot time precision:** The percentage of records for which precise temporal information (day and month) is provided
- **Data verification:** Identification verification status of the records that they provided
- **Data usability:** Licence type of the records that they provided

We provide further details for each of these attributes below.

Number of taxon groups Data providers often provide data for a subset of the taxon groups. In this sense, data providers differ in terms of their species and taxon focus. In this section we will use a classification into 9 taxon groups. Table 6 shows the number of data providers that provided data by the number of taxon groups that they provided data for. Table 7 shows the top 10 data providers who provided data for one taxon group only. The ranking is based on a number of records they provided.

Number of records Table 8 shows the number of records provided by the top 6 data providers and the percentage of those over the total number of records. The first 11 providers provided 90% of the total number of records in the dataset.

No. taxon groups	No. data providers	No. records
1	42	1,273,781
2	18	485,875
3	11	209,722
4	8	24,107
5	7	6,766,624
6	5	84,575
7	9	175,213
8	7	338,489
9	13	844,543

Table 6: Number of data providers for each taxon group.

Rank	Data provider	Taxon group	No. records
1	UK Butterfly Monitoring Scheme	invert	602,653
2	Butterfly Conservation	invert	597,447
3	Berkshire Moth Group	invert	16,238
4	British Lichen Society	fungi	11,972
5	British Dragonfly Society Recording Scheme	invert	10,753
6	Sheffield Bird Study Group	birds	8,051
7	British Bryological Society	nvplants	7,068
8	Marine Conservation Society	marine	6,928
9	Bumblebee Conservation Trust	invert	1,910
10	Soldierflies and Allies Recording Scheme	invert	1,883

Table 7: Top 10 data providers who provided records in one taxon group only. The ranking is based on the number of records they provided.

Spot place precision Table 9 shows the precision of the location of records in the dataset, categorised into 3 sizes (up to 1km, between 1km and 10km and more than 10km). It can be seen that the majority of the observations were provided with a reasonable level of resolution. The percentages of records provided by a data provider for each of these categories are the three attributes included in the clustering analysis.

Rank	Data Provider	No. records	Proportion
1	British Trust for Ornithology	6,734,841	66.01%
2	UK Butterfly Monitoring Scheme	602,653	5.91%
3	Butterfly Conservation	597,447	5.86%
4	People's Trust for Endangered Species	193,649	1.90%
5	Royal Society for the Protection of Birds	192,574	1.89%
6	Norfolk Biodiversity Information Service	182,681	1.79%

Table 8: Number of records provided by the top 6 data providers and the percentage of those over the total number of records.

Resolution	No. records	Percentage of records
0-1 Km	6,252,024	61.28%
1 Km to 10 Km	3,934,072	38.56%
More than 10 Km	487	0%
Not Provided	16,346	0.16%

Table 9: Precision of the location of records in the dataset

Spot time precision For some records the day and the month of the recording are missing: 20.50% of the records are missing the day and 4.27% of the records are missing the month. The percentages of records provided by a data provider at each level of time precision are the two attributes included in the clustering analysis: the percentage of records with the full data, and the percentage of records for which only the month is available.

Data verification 94.24% of the records provided have been identified and verified. 2.49% are unconfirmed, while 3.27% have not been reviewed. The percentages of records provided by a data provider for each level of data verification are the attributes included in the clustering analysis: the percentage of records which have been identified and verified and the percentage of records which have not been reviewed.

Data usability Data providers have shared data with NBN Trust either as an open (99.60%) or shared license (0.4%).

5.2.2 Describing data providers using attributes

We can represent the attributes above for each data provider using radar plots. A radar plot displays multivariate data in the form of a two-dimensional chart of quantitative variables represented on axes originating from the center. See Figure 22 for an example of radar plots for 4 data providers, showing 9 attributes as percentages: up to 1km, between 1km to 10km, more than 10km, gs presented, day presented, month presented, IVS accepted, IVS not reviewed, and license open.

Figure 22: Radar plots examples for four individual data providers

5.2.3 Results

We used the attributes to cluster the data providers to classify them into groups that are more easily understood. We used the Hopkins statistic [3] to assess the clustering tendency of the data set by measuring the probability that a given data set is not random, with 1 indicating highly clustered data, 0.5 indicating random data and 0 uniformly distributed data. The result of the Hopkins test was 0.87, indicating a promising clustering ability.

To find the optimum number of clusters the silhouette coefficient metric was used. The silhouette coefficient measures how similar an object is to the other objects in its own cluster versus those in the neighbouring clusters. A value of close to 1 indicates that the object is well clustered and values range from 1 to -1. Different numbers of clusters were tested using the k-means clustering algorithm and the highest average silhouette coefficient of 0.6710 indicated the optimum number of clusters is 4.

Figure 23 shows radar plots for each of the four clusters by averaging the data providers' attributes. Cluster 4 includes 67 data providers and they are characterised by highly precise and open data. Cluster 3 includes 8 data providers which are characterised by missing date information. Cluster 2 includes 17 data providers which are characterised by their unverified identification data. Cluster 1 includes 30 data providers which are characterised by providing mean values for the attributes.

Weaknesses and limitations The attributes that are used to cluster data providers are percentages used to include categorical variables. As such, some variables have constraints, as their sum should be equal to or less than one if not all categories of a variable have been included. Extensions of the k-means algorithm might be better suited to this type of data. Additionally, the information on species classification into groups could be improved, utilising true taxonomic groups rather than the given UKBAP Level 1 classification groups. Finally, the location of data providers could be included as an additional attribute.

Figure 23: Radar plots representing the average attributes for the four clusters of data providers

5.3 Data Provider Dashboard

To highlight the impact of individual data providers, we developed a prototype for a data provider dashboard displaying the contributions of a single data provider. The main objectives of this visualisation are to:

- Visualise the regions and species for which a given provider contributes biodiversity records.
- Allow the user to explore how these contributions have varied over time, on both the species and regional dimensions.
- Highlight the impact that the data provider has created for the NBN Atlas through their contributions.
- Allow exploration of ways the provider can contribute in the future in

order to make the most impact.

For the purposes of this DSG, we first developed a design mockup to identify features and visualisation components that would be useful to include in the dashboard in order to meet the above aims. We then developed an interactive prototype based on this design, for which we included ten data providers as examples of how the final version could look. We present a summary of the features of this prototype, as well as suggestions for features which could be incorporated into a final version in future work.

Design Mockup As a first step, we created a mockup to identify the visualisation components for inclusion in our prototype or a scaled version developed in the future. This mockup is displayed in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Design mockup displaying the imagined features for a data provider dashboard. The mockup is for exploratory purposes only and does not display real data.

From this mockup, we extracted a list of features which could be included in a final version of the data provider dashboard. Some of these may be more or less appropriate for certain providers or may need to be adapted.

The identified features, and some examples of potentially necessary adaptations, are as follows:

- An interactive map displaying the headquarters of the data provider and the location of all the biodiversity records they have contributed. Interactive elements will include the ability to zoom on the map and to hover over records to receive more information using a tooltip. The scale of the map will need to be adapted for providers covering different areas (e.g. local, regional or national).
- Fundamental facts and statistics about the contributions of the data provider, including (but possibly not limited to):
 - The total number of records
 - The number of unique species among these records
 - Some measure of the spatial spread of the records (in our mockup, this is displayed as the average distance to the headquarters, though other metrics could be considered such as the total area covered, bounded by the most distant records)
 - The proportion of the provided records of a given resolution
- Area or line plots for each individual species recorded by the provider, showing the number of that species identified in each year. As the number of species for one provider may be large, for some providers it may be more desirable to group by taxon or to display only the top ten most prominent species in their records. Additionally, these plots can be displayed without axes to avoid visual clutter, and a tooltip can be used to display numeric values when the mouse hovers over a point on the graph.
- Similar area or line plots for particular regions or districts rather than particular species, with buttons to toggle between species plots and spatial plots. The inclusion of spatial plots will only be appropriate where the provider covers an area which is meaningfully segmented.
- The ability to click on individual species plots to filter the records displayed on the map.
- A temporal slider allowing filtering of both the map and the species plots according to a given year range, input by the user.

- A one-line summary of a particular impact or contribution of the given data provider, for example "this provider contributed 70% of biodiversity records in Nottingham in the NBN Atlas". This feature would be highly data provider-specific and is not included in our mockup.
- An indicator highlights the species that the data provider has missing records of during a certain period of time.

Prototype After producing this design mockup, we then developed an initial prototype to display some of the features in a dashboard. Our primary tools for the development of this dashboard were the Plotly and Dash packages in Python. While these were suitable to develop a prototype quickly during the DSG, as discussed later in the report, they would not be suitable for a larger project. For this prototype, we restricted ourselves to just ten of the data providers who shared species records between 2010 and 2020, to limit scope as the requirements of the visualisation for some providers will vary. The sample data providers include Sheffield and Rotherham Wildlife Trust, UK Butterfly Monitoring Scheme, Marine Biological Association, Natural History Museum, London, Bumblebee Conservation Trust, Marine Conservation Society, Bat Conservation Trust, People's Trust for Endangered Species, Isle of Wight Local Records Centre, and Dorset Environmental Records Centre. These ten were chosen randomly from those without a significantly large or significantly small number of records. In Figure 25 below, we display a screenshot of the prototype dashboard, with the omission of the data provider radar plot. This is an additional feature which we included later, based on the analysis in Section 5.2.

In this screenshot, we display real data from the Bumblebee Conservation Trust between the years 2010 and 2020. The prototype we have developed features many of the components we envisaged in our mockup, including the interactive map, the ability to filter by year and species, some simple statistics on the data provider and line plots for species record occurrence over the time period. Additionally, development of a fully scaled dashboard for all data providers is a project with a far larger scope.

Figure 25: Screenshot of the data provider dashboard prototype

Web development We created a prototype of a web service allowing users to explore the outputs of the species distribution model across different vice-counties. Such a tool also provides a comparison between predictions of the model and actual observations available in the NBN Atlas (Figure 26). The user is able to choose the year of interest, species, vice-county, and finally descriptive statistics to display on the map, e.g. one could consider a map for the standard error of the distribution prediction of the house sparrow in 2018 with actual records shown or not.

The interactive map portion of the website allows for a higher resolution

Figure 26: Prototype of the webpage

investigation of the prediction model (Figure 27). This is particularly useful for organising and planning future steps by an organisation or individuals. Someone interested in the distribution or sighting of a specific species is able to recognise which areas they should visit by using such a map.

Weaknesses and limitations In building this prototype, we encountered the following challenges:

1. Limited supported visualisation features available on Plotly. Some functionality proved difficult to implement, such as showing the headquarters of the data providers on the map, and searching by the species name.
2. The scalability of the Dash framework. When working with a large number of rows in the dataframe and a variety of visualisations for inclusion on the dashboard, the performance of Dash became impaired and the prototype ran slowly. Consequently, we needed to reduce both the number of data providers and species records, and

Figure 27: Interactive map design for each county and model predictions.

perform some pre-calculation of statistics before feeding these into the dashboard.

Future Work Immediate areas of future work could focus on further development of the prototype to include additional features or additional data providers, and a full-scale development of a web application version of the data provider dashboard, depending on the degree of interest of the challenge owner. If a final version of this application is to be built, alternative tooling with greater scalability and wider functionality should be explored.

One additional interesting avenue of future work could be the inclusion of a “suggestion” algorithm, which identifies on the dashboard areas where the provider could add additional impact. This algorithm could assess suggestions of different types to identify those which may have the greatest impact, for example:

- Coverage of certain underrepresented sub-regions in the area already covered by the data provider
- Further exploration of species which the data provider has found in small numbers or restricted areas
- Increased resolution of biodiversity records

For a data provider with good area coverage but poor resolution, the latter may be more impactful, or vice versa in the opposite case. The output of this suggestion algorithm could be presented alongside some visualisations developed in Section 5.2. Overall, this suggestion could encourage data providers to continue supplying good quality of species data in the long term.

5.4 Occurrence Density Discrepancy For Identifying Low Coverage Species (ODDFILCS)

5.4.1 Methods

To identify species that do not have coverage, we developed a method for prioritising species based on discrepancies in occurrence record density

in a target area compared to a comparison region, called ODDFILCS. This approach attempts to highlight species for enhanced data collection by identifying species with occurrence data that is at a lower density than we might anticipate if we assumed that they occurred at a similar frequency in the target and comparison region. In the broader gap identification workflow, we envisage that this method would form an intermediate step between the national scale mapping approaches and species specific targeting of locations where to record.

This method is an application of a 'reasonable comparison' framework we conceptualised as part of the DSG. We first define a context that we are interested in within the 4 key dimensions that we can partition the data: space, time, species and data provider; for example, let us say that we are interested in birds in the Cambridgeshire vice-county from 2010-2020 for all data providers. The summary statistics you can calculate such as number of records, number of species etc. are of limited usefulness without a reasonable comparison. For example, a comparison might be for the same taxonomic group and time period but for a different geographic region with similar biogeographic conditions. This would allow you to determine if the number of records/species in your target area is due to differences in recording effort or the relative contribution of data providers.

There however are considerations when attempting to make "reasonable comparisons". For example, different environmental conditions of different regions may affect the relative densities of species occurrence records. For example comparing a landlocked region to a coastal region is unlikely to be a reasonable comparison as marine species may be highlighted as under-recorded in the target region compared to the comparison region. Highlighting marine species as high priority would be due to marine species not being found inland, rather than indicating that action should be taken to collect more data on marine species.

The first step in the ODDFILCS approach consists in defining the area of interest (hereafter *target* area) and choosing a sensible, if much larger, comparison area (i.e. *background* area). Linking back to the example above, the target area would be the Cambridgeshire vice-county and a sensible choice of background region would be the corresponding biogeographic zone [1] or the nation as a whole. Figure 28 shows an example

Figure 28: Example of target (right) and background (left) areas in the ODDFILCS approach for the analysis of species coverage in Northamptonshire.

of the relation between target and background areas.

Next, the occurrence density of records (d) for each species within the target areas and the background area is calculated. This is defined as the number of records (r) of a species (s_i) in the NBN Atlas divided by the surface area (A_k) of the region considered (with k = target or background).

$$d(s_i, A_k) = \frac{r(s_i)}{A_k}.$$

To define whether a species is locally under-recorded, the relative ratio between the occurrence density of records of the target and background areas is calculated. As a species might be barely present in one area or, on the contrary, is associated to a large number of recordings due to a very active data provider, these ratios span several orders of magnitude.

For this reason, we define the "ODD score" as the natural logarithm of the occurrence density ratios:

$$ODD(s_i) = \log \left(\frac{d(s_i, A_{target})}{d(s_i, A_{background})} \right).$$

Species with a positive ODD score are recorded more often in the target than in the background area; a negative ODD score indicates, instead, that the species is under-recorded in that specific region. Hence, the ODD score allows to rank the species living in a specific area based on the associated NBN Atlas coverage.

For a better visualisation of the ODD score rank, the species have been grouped in the associated taxonomic group based on the level 1 from the UK BAP classification scheme. For example, we can define thresholds, such as the first and third quartile of the density distribution of the ODD scores for each taxonomic group, and assess the NBN Atlas' coverage of species in relation to the thresholds. In this example, species below the first quartile are potentially under-recorded, while species above the third quartile are recorded more often in the target than in the background area, or have a data provider that is active in that area. An example of the density distribution of the ODD scores for the taxonomic group present in the Atlas is shown in top part of Figure 29.

5.4.2 Application

To demonstrate how this looks in action we developed a prototype web application using R Shiny, shown in Figure 29. For this demonstration we defined the following target and background:

Target: occurrence records within a specified vice-county, for all species, across all years, for all data providers.

Background: occurrence records within all areas of England except the target vice-county, for all species, for all years, for all data providers.

We provided user controls to enable a user to select a vice-county. The Shiny application then generates the ODD scores for all species observed in the target area. Distributions of the ODD scores are visualised in a

density plot faceted by taxonomic group. A table provided to allow the user to look at the ODD scores of each species. The table can be filtered by taxonomic group of interest.

Occurrence Density Discrepancy for Identifying Low Coverage Species (ODDFILCS)

Figure 29: ODDFILCS app showing information for the Cambridgeshire vice-county

The table also provides some supplementary information: the number of occurrences in the target area, the main provider of that species and the % of records that are of 'high' spatial resolution; 1km x 1km grid size or finer. It can be searched for specific taxa and sorted by ODD score, number of occurrences or % of high resolution records.

Weaknesses and limitations The ODDFILCS method can be used to select under-recorded species only when the target and background areas

are biogeographically similar. For instance, the ODD scores obtained from a mountain region would not be meaningful if they are calculated using a maritime background.

A further issue is that the ODDFILCS analysis takes into account only the species already known to live in the target area. For instance, in Cambridgeshire, only 240 of the 911 UK priority species have been recorded. ODDFILCS is a method to rank the coverage of these species but does not provide any indication on whether any of the missing 671 species is likely to be living there. Therefore, these species that have no records in the target area are not presented within the current framework. However, this is a significant omission as the lowest coverage species are those with no records and we currently simply ignore them from the species list. Given the presented background region of England, this list will contain species that are unlikely to be present due to unsuitable environmental conditions within the target area, and the current ODDFILCS framework provides no way to filter this list (potentially of hundreds of species) to only include relevant species. As discussed in Section 5.1, there are severe gaps in species coverage in the dataset.

Species that are infrequently recorded in a few vice-counties, consistently appear as high ODD scores. For example, we found that non-vascular plants consistently appeared to have high ODD scores. This was because they were so infrequently recorded, and in combination with the filtering only for species that appeared in the vice-county, meaning only high ODD score species tended to appear.

Furthermore, the ODD scores are calculated without taking into account the resolution of the species records. Records at higher resolution provide more information. Including occurrence data with low spatial resolution might falsely indicate that there is good quality data available for a species, when in reality the data is not at a usable spatial resolution. This could potentially lead to wrong inferences for those species whose records are associated to a resolution larger than the size of the target area, or located at the edge of the target area.

Future Work A possible extension within the ODDFILCS approach is to consider the temporal dimension of the records in the NBN Atlas to

assess the taxonomic coverage throughout time. In this case, a "reasonable comparison" would be between the abundance of records of one taxon group in a specific year against the median number of records for all the others in that year. This can be again quantified as the logarithm of the ratio between the two quantities (i.e. a temporal ODD score). The time series of temporal ODD scores would allow to visualise temporal discrepancies in species coverage with over-sampled taxon group having positive temporal ODD scores and under-recorded ones with a negative temporal ODD scores. This analysis would also allow an overview of the recording rate for each taxonomic group by determining the slope of the best-fit line. This would enable a snapshot view of which species and/or taxon groups are seeing an increase or decrease in the availability of occurrence data on the NBN Atlas.

Increased flexibility in the ability to fine-tune the target and background filters would increase the usefulness of an interactive ODDFILCS application. Being able to specify custom geographic regions would allow providers that operate outside of the vice-county system to determine low coverage species within their operational boundary. Being able to specify a background region would allow data providers to use their local knowledge to select representative regions and facilitate reasonable comparisons.

Development of a composite index/score that incorporates other information alongside the ODD score might be able to more usefully rank species that have low coverage. For example a composite score could combine the percentage of records that are of a certain threshold of resolution, assigning more weight to recent records and incorporating a model-derived measure of probability of occurrence.

5.5 Representing coverage and gaps in the Atlas

To represent the coverage of the NBN Atlas and to represent some of its gaps, we assessed the distribution of the sampling strategy across each vice-county. To achieve this, we defined the Normalized Spatial Sampling Variance (SSV) measure. We defined the SSV_{kj} for taxon group k and vice-county j as:

$$SSV_{jk} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{jk}} \left(\frac{X_i - \bar{X}_j}{X_{j,\max} - X_{j,\min}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{Y_i - \bar{Y}_j}{Y_{j,\max} - Y_{j,\min}} \right)^2$$

where X_i is the longitude and Y_i is the latitude for the i_{th} record in each county j for each taxon group k , $X_{j,\max}$, $Y_{j,\max}$, $X_{j,\min}$, $Y_{j,\min}$ and \bar{X} , \bar{Y} are the maximum, minimum and average of the longitude and latitude respectively for each county j , and n_{jk} is the number of records in each county j for each taxon group k .

When it comes to the vice-county level, there exists a strong correlation between the SSV and the vice-county areas. Larger vice-counties tend to have more widely dispersed sampling records than smaller vice-counties. Consequently, North Lincolnshire, being one of the largest areas, exhibits the highest SSV, while smaller counties such as Bedfordshire and Huntingdonshire manifest lower SSV.

Nonetheless, the SSV underscores the necessity for more evenly distributed sampling in certain counties. For instance, despite South-west Yorkshire having the highest total occurrences, its SSV ranks in the middle. This implies that records in this county are collected more densely in a restricted area. Further exploration is warranted to devise a more effective sampling strategy. By enabling data providers to better capture the breadth of UK biodiversity, this approach could yield more representative data and more robust conclusions.

6 Conclusions

The main achievements of the DSG are the development of new approaches, a new metric and prototypes of interactive online dashboards. Our approaches were based on different angles: species, data providers, and geographical comparisons.

First of all, we looked at species distribution. Combining the NBN trust data with environmental data from external sources, we developed a model to predict the distribution of species. There is evidence that this model has the potential to adequately predict the presence of each species given the environmental conditions, land cover data and survey

effort. Moreover, we demonstrated that this model can show data providers the influence of their data upon insights into species, as model predictions of species distributions change with and without their data. This species distribution model was included in a prototype of an online dashboard allowing users to explore the outputs of the species distribution model across different vice-counties. This is particularly useful for organising and planning future steps by an organisation or individuals. Someone interested in the distribution or sighting of a specific species is able to recognise which areas they should visit by using such a map.

Then we focused on data providers, to highlight the value that each brings to the dataset and to identify gaps. We analysed their attributes and then clustered them to understand their characteristics more easily. Then, we developed a prototype for a data provider dashboard displaying the contributions of a single data provider as well as their defining characteristics as identified by the clustering method.

We then focused on geographical distribution of data and, to identify species that do not have coverage, we developed a method for prioritising species based on discrepancies in occurrence record density in a target area compared to a comparison region. This approach attempts to highlight species for enhanced data collection by identifying species with occurrence data that is at a lower density than we might anticipate. To represent the coverage of the NBN Atlas and to represent some of its gaps, we also assessed the distribution of the sampling strategy across each vice-county. Both these methods were developed as prototype web applications.

7 Future work and research avenues

The DSG was very successful in identifying a number of avenues for research, new approaches and prototypes for online dashboards. All the methods that we suggested are intended to provide a starting point, as they all require further development and refinement, as well as full deployment to the full dataset.

Developing and deploying the three online dashboards suggested in this

report is a very promising avenue as they would provide users of the NBN Trust with evidence to drive their future research, whether that is data collection or data analysis.

The models require further work, as the limited time of the DSG did not allow a full exploration of the model specifications. However, we provided here an overview of the value that these models can bring to the understanding of the NBN Trust data.

We did not have enough time to consider the temporal dimension of the records in the NBN Atlas to assess the taxonomic coverage throughout time. This would enable a snapshot view of which species and/or taxon groups are seeing an increase or decrease in the availability of occurrence data on the NBN Atlas.

It is paramount to encourage data providers to continue supplying good quality of species data in the long term. Therefore, an important suggestion for future work is to develop an algorithm that identifies the areas that would most increase the impact that each data provider has to the NBN Atlas.

Within the limited time of the DSG, we have focused our efforts mainly on geographical representation of the data. Another potentially insightful way to visualise the data could be by taxonomic groups, e.g. using dendrograms to separate the species into phylogenetic groups, and representing metrics such as percentages of total occurrences or percentages of unique species next to each individual group. Visualising the data in this way could help researchers and funding bodies to gain a better overview which taxonomic groups could benefit from increased efforts in sampling and sharing of observation records.

8 Team members

Figure 30: The Data Study Group participants, facilitators and PI.

Khushboo Gurung is a Research Fellow at the School of Earth and Environment, University of Leeds. Her research focuses on investigating the impact of plant evolution on Earth's paleoclimate using models. She contributed towards the environment-based gap identification for target species section of this report.

Corinna Hartinger is a PhD student in the Department of Biology at the University of Oxford (and member of the OxUni Ceilidh Band). Her research interests lie in plant metabolic modelling for crop improvement. She contributed to the challenge by conceptualisation of diverse approaches, visualisations and presentation.

Silvia Liverani is Reader in Statistics at Queen Mary University of London and Turing Fellow. Her research interests are in Bayesian statistical models and her expertise is on clustering methods and spatio-temporal modelling. She was the Principal Investigator (PI) for this challenge.

Hao Ni is a 2nd PhD student in Electrical, electronic and systems

Engineering at the University of Birmingham and Birmingham Centre for Railway Research and Education(BCRRE). He focuses on the application of artificial intelligence and ML methods to capture tacit knowledge in railway signalling. He contributed to this project using geographical data to map the data in a real national scale visualisation.

Pornpanit Rasivisuth is a 2nd year PhD student in Venture Capital and Private Equity at University College London. Her research interest focuses on machine learning and natural language processing application in startup valuation and portfolio company due diligence for the venture capital fund. She contributed to this project by developing the data provider dashboard alongside Sophie.

Fusun Recal is an Assistant Professor in Industrial Engineering Department at Isik University, Istanbul. Her research interests are in data driven decision making and her expertise is on supervised and unsupervised machine learning modeling. She contributed to this project using radar plots and k-means clustering to analyze data providers in terms of their tendency on providing usable and non-missing data.

Simon Rolph is a data scientist at the UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology. He works with biodiversity data, typically from citizen science. He contributed towards the ODDFILCS method development and was one of the two facilitators for the group.

Sophie Sadler is a final year PhD student in Explainable AI at Swansea University, with a variety of previous machine learning experience in companies such as Meta and Microsoft Research. She contributed to this project by developing the data provider dashboard alongside Pornpanit. She was also one of the two facilitators for the group.

Andrea Sante is a PhD student in Astrophysics at Liverpool John Moores University. His research focuses in reconstructing the assembly history of the Milky-Way using cosmological simulations and deep learning techniques. He contributed towards the ODDFILCS method development.

Fiona Seaton is a quantitative ecologist within the UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology, based in Lancaster. Her experience is largely in the statistical analysis of ecological field surveys across Great Britain to evaluate state and change in plant and soil condition. She contributed to

the environment-based gap identification for target species section of this report.

Alisa Sheinkman is a third-year Ph.D. student at the University of Edinburgh. She has a Pure Math background and her thesis focuses on Efficient inference schemes in Bayesian Neural Networks. She contributed towards the environment-based gap identification for target species section of this report.

Dongyu Zheng, a quantitative geologist, serves as a Visiting Research Fellow at the University of Leeds and an Associate Professor at Chengdu University of Technology, China. He specializes in sedimentary petrology and petroleum geology. His current work focuses on leveraging deep learning for automated rock thin-section identification and paleogeographic reconstruction. In this project, he contributed statistical analysis and visual comparisons across multiple vice-counties.

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**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

**turing.ac.uk
@turinginst**